

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Grid Ancillary Services Provision by Electric vehicles and Renewable distributed generation
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	GRASPER
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Technical University of Denmark SYSLAB (PowerLabDK)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Charging stations Distributed energy resources Electric vehicle Energy storage Fault ride-through behaviour Power distribution faults Power distribution network Power system restoration Solar panels Vehicle-to-grid
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	25/08/2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	08/09/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	26/09/2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	06/09/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	2
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	weekend
Number of days using the RI	10
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	The project originally had two users, but one of them could not join the visit
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Characterise fault ride-through behaviour of groups of electric vehicles / electric vehicle chargers and solar photovoltaic inverters to verify whether they remain in operation over a range of scenarios (defined by voltage and frequency deviations and disconnection from the distribution substation). 	

2. Verify whether electric vehicles / electric vehicle chargers and solar photovoltaic panels can be re-energised after being disconnected from the distribution substation over a range of operating conditions.
3. Verify the ability of electric vehicles / electric vehicle chargers and solar photovoltaic inverters to support re-energisation of parts of the network in the aftermath of a power outage.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The following activities were performed during the experimental tests:

1. *Power grid setup: connection of power grid components (namely, electric vehicles, solar photovoltaic panels, and loads) to a grid-forming inverter-based generator.*
2. *Measurement setup, including meters at network buses (rms values) and an oscilloscope (waveform signals), and a Python script to collect measurements.*
3. *Operating condition setup: define voltage and frequency setpoint at the Python script initialisation.*
4. *Disconnection / reconnection setup: disconnection of power grid components from the grid-forming generator, followed by reconnection after a few seconds.*
5. *Data collection setup: waveform signal capture when first re-energisation attempt occurs, rms values saved as csv file.*
6. *End of test.*

The following activities were performed after the experimental analysis:

7. *Comparison between experimental results and requirements defined by the Danish Guide.*
8. *Plot rms values and waveform signals.*

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Experimental results show that:

- The PV inverters do not fully comply with the voltage and frequency requirements for mandatory operation and disconnection. Most of them disconnected at higher grid frequencies than 50.0 Hz, and not all of them disconnected in compliance with the overvoltage / undervoltage / underfrequency requirements.
- The EVs behave in different ways when subject to voltage and frequency disturbances. Some of them do not reconnect under operating conditions when they are expected to, while others always reconnect under operating conditions when they shall cease to operate. The main compliance problems occur during undervoltage (EVs disconnecting or reconnecting when they should not), overfrequency (EVs reconnecting when they should not), underfrequency (EVs disconnecting when they should not).

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

From the experimental results, it can be concluded that:

1. The fault ride-through behaviour of the tested electric vehicles and solar photovoltaic inverters does not fully comply with Green Power Denmark's "Guide for connection of power generating plants to the low voltage grid (≤ 1 kV). The tested electric vehicles and solar photovoltaic inverters cannot remain in operation over a range of scenarios defined

by voltage and frequency deviations and disconnection from the distribution substation as per the Danish Guide.

2. The tested electric vehicles / electric vehicle chargers and solar photovoltaic panels can be re-energised after being disconnected from the distribution substation over a range of operating conditions. However, these operating conditions do not fully meet the requirements defined by the Danish Guide. As the penetration of distributed energy resources increases, there will likely be more power quality and stability problems at distribution voltage levels caused by mismatches between required and actual operating performance.
3. The tested electric vehicles / electric vehicle chargers and solar photovoltaic inverters can support re-energisation of parts of the network in the aftermath of a power outage under certain conditions. However, their fault-ride through behaviour do not fully meet the requirements defined by the Danish Guide. Therefore, their ability to fully support re-energisation of parts of the network in the aftermath of a power outage is limited to certain operating conditions on a case-by-case basis.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

The experimental set up allowed for a god variety of tests involving different models of electric vehicles and solar photovoltaic panels. With this, it was possible:

1. *to test a wide range of operating conditions involving different distributed energy resources over the duration of the visit,*
2. *to verify the fault ride-through behaviour of different distributed energy resources and their ability to be re-energised after disconnection from the distribution substation,*
3. *to capture active and reactive power measurements and voltage and current waveform signals after a re-energisation attempt.*

Tests were as comprehensive as possible given the short visit duration and will lay the foundations for future work looking into fault ride-through behaviour and wider impacts on power grids.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

No problems in getting access to the necessary equipment, facilities, and measurements. Although the vehicle-to-grid component was not available, other tests were performed in substitution to those involving the vehicle-to-grid component. Repeating these experiments using the vehicle-to-grid component and other electric vehicle models could make a good case for another visit.

Intended publications

The outcomes of my project work will be published open access in scientific journals (e.g., Elsevier's Energy / Energy Policy / International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems), with possible extensions to high-impact analyses (e.g., Nature Energy / Communications).

Data management

The project data will be further used in scientific publications and stored by the user group leader in compliance with the University of Bath's research data management policy.

Conclusions / additional comments

No further comments.

<p>Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No e6fb440c-4d84-40bb-b846-a6d065f773b3</p>						
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction						
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments						
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process		1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>The information about the application process was very clear. The RI provider promptly clarified my questions about their facilities.</i>						
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed		1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>The information about next steps was clear, but the contract needed some amendments which took several months to be finalised.</i>						
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics		Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
N/A.						
RI extension / upgrades required		In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
N/A.						
Problems with local regulations		Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
N/A.						
Health and safety issues		Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

N/A.	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
N/A.	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
N/A.	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
N/A.	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
N/A.	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
N/A.	
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
N/A.	
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
N/A.	

Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Timely communication as needed.</i>					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
<i>Different types of energy storage technologies to test (e.g., heavy-duty electric vehicles).</i>					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
<i>Improving the contract model would certainly help improve future TNA programmes. Increasing the range of energy storage technologies and experimental tests would enable the achievement of higher TRLs.</i>					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>I read the WP descriptions on the project website.</i>					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>I have never learned how to take advantage of it.</i>					
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>I know it exists in the project WPs, but not that TNA users can take advantage of it.</i>					

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.